

Leveraging LLM Reasoning for Knowledge Graph Construction: Capabilities, Methodologies, and Implications

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Abstract

In this paper we introduce a formal approach which employs Reasoning Large Language Models for constructing knowledge graphs (KGs) from historical documents. The method combines named entity recognition techniques with LLM reasoning to align named entities with all their mentions in historic texts and to extract context-aware relationships with supporting evidence. The extracted information is structured to build a knowledge graph, prepared for import, visualization, navigation and validation with the use of graph databases. While the experimental evaluation employs *GPT-5 Thinking* for LLM reasoning and Neo4j for storing the knowledge graph, the Knowledge Graph construction workflow formalizes the processing pipeline, which can be transcoded and implemented with alternative reasoning LLMs and different graph databases. This approach is validated by analyzing the *Dumitru Nistor's War Diary*, a historic document rich in mentions of named entities (i.e. persons, organizations, locations) and historical events related to the first world war. An example for employing this process to generate knowledge graph representations for historical documents, and to generate meaningful visualizations with minimal human oversight is showcased in the paper.

Keywords

Knowledge Graph, Large Reasoning Models, Named Entity Recognition, Transcribathon, Digital Humanities

1. Introduction

Knowledge graphs (KGs) have become a core technology for representing structured knowledge in a machine-readable format, supporting applications such as semantic search, intelligent question answering, and reasoning-based inference [1]. Unlike traditional KG pipelines that typically extract semantic information from large-scale unstructured data, our approach extends the Named Entity Recognition and Linking (NERL) techniques with the *thinking* capability provided by Large Reasoning Models (LRM) such as GPT-5. We validate this approach by constructing KGs from large textual documents containing rich descriptive information of historical events, such as war diaries from the first world war.

The proposed solution aims to support the core activities of digital Cultural Heritage (CH) and Digital Humanities domains which target the extraction of semantic information from textual resources or semi-structured data to build knowledge graphs, enabling advanced search, visualization and navigation through large CH repositories, and consequently, providing valuable tools for history research. One of the main challenges in this context, still lies in linking identified entities with their mentions in large corpora, consolidating their aliases in controlled multilingual vocabularies, and discovering relationships between these entities across heterogeneous data sources. While NERL tools support the analysis of historical documents by identifying contextual entities, their validation and the proper representation in standardized semantic models is still a time consuming activity.

New opportunities arise with the development of Large Reasoning Models, they provide basic functionality for discovering relationships between entities, establishing processing pipelines based on LLM reasoning and automatic building of knowledge graph representations. LRMs like GPT-5

introduce improvements in reasoning, context handling, and instruction adherence over earlier models, enabling fine-grained relation typing, entity consolidation, and evidence attribution in downstream graphs [2, 3]. By using these capabilities, the proposed approach aims at building proper semantic representations for complex historical contexts such as military campaigns or multiple events connected to large scale conflicts. This approach is validated by analyzing *Dumitru Nistor's War Diary*, a document that presents experiences of a soldier traveling over a half of the world while serving for several years on the "SMS Kaiserin Elisabeth" battle cruiser during the World War I. The original document contains about 180 pages of handwritten text in Romanian language, still it often includes paragraphs in German or Hungarian, and named entities from foreign languages, which are simply transliterated with Romanian alphabet. This situation is often found in war diaries, when simple soldiers are describing their experiences from people and locations in foreign countries about they never heard before.

The contribution of this paper consist in constructing a reproducible workflow for analyzing historical documents with use of LRMS. It leverages *LRM reasoning* for context-sensitive relation extraction and alias resolution for entities identified with a previously developed NERL tool [4], referencing evidences in the original text, and producing a knowledge graph representation ready for import in graph databases (i.e. Neo4j). This paper demonstrates how transformer-based generative models can use semi-structured data extracted from historical documents to construct a domain specific KGs, and lower the technical barrier for non-specialists, and facilitate their adoption in daily activities. While the proposed approach is evaluated on a small dataset (i.e. single but complex document), the processing workflow is generic and scalable. This can be extended for analysing many similar documents available in Europeana WWI collection¹ being manually or automatically transcribed. The main limitation still resides in the necessity to validate the the automatically detected entity relationships. To ensure the scalability of the proposed approach, this work is planned to be integrated in the Transcribathon² tool, a crowdsourcing & citizen-science platform which employs the human-in-the-loop methodology for transcription and semantical enrichment of historical documents. While reasoning LLMs are emerging technologies nowadays, it is expected that entity relationships will be recognized with higher precision with the next generations of LLMs.

2. Related Work

Knowledge graphs offer a powerful framework for representing rich semantic information. However, their construction faces persistent challenges of scalability, contextual accuracy, and alias consolidation. Recent work has shown that LLMs can alleviate many of these difficulties, and advances in LRM reasoning expand opportunities for hybrid pipelines that combine structured metadata with model-driven inference [5, 6]. Research on domain knowledge graphs increasingly stresses the necessity of human-in-the-loop workflows to ensure accuracy, particularly when extracting knowledge from complex unstructured texts. In power-grid applications, Xiao et al. highlight how schema design, rule-based extraction, and expert validation remain essential for resolving ambiguity and maintaining reliable KG structures despite partial automation [7]. The approach proposed in this paper builds on this insight and introduces the use of reasoning-LLMs to reduce efforts for manual validation of the extracted information through context-aware entity alignment and relation extraction. While still enabling lightweight expert oversight to correct uncertain or low-confidence entity relationships, the paper adopts the emerging paradigm for LLM-assisted KG construction.

Hogan *et al.* synthesize a definition of KGs as graphs of data that accumulate and convey knowledge about the real world, where nodes represent entities of interest and edges encode semantic relations among them [8]. This formalism enables structured reasoning over heterogeneous sources, with flexibility for integrating new information and maintaining contextual links between entities. Ji *et al.* [1] highlight the widespread adoption of KGs in applications such as semantic search, intelligent question answering, and reasoning-based inference.

¹<https://www.europeana.eu/en/themes/world-war-i>

²<https://europeana.transcribathon.eu/documents/?q=diary&entity=story&offset=1>

Figure 1: Knowledge Graph Building Workflow

Recent research investigates how large language models (LLMs) can address these limitations. Pan *et al.* [9] propose a roadmap for unifying LLMs and KGs, distinguishing KG-enhanced LLMs, LLM-augmented KGs, and synergistic frameworks. Bhatt *et al.* [5] empirically compare GPT-4, LLaMA 2, and BERT for KG construction, finding that LLMs outperform classical approaches in semantic fidelity and structural accuracy. McCusker [6] introduces LOKE-GPT, a prompt-engineered framework for triple extraction that outperforms OpenIE while exposing challenges like over-generation.

The GPT-5 model family marks a significant advancement in LLM capabilities. OpenAI reports improved reasoning, multimodal integration, and instruction adherence [2]. Georgiou [3] provides early empirical evidence of GPT-5’s superior performance across reasoning-centric domains. These advances make GPT-5—particularly the *Thinking* variant—well-suited for context-sensitive tasks in KG construction, such as relation typing, alias consolidation, and evidence attribution.

3. Knowledge Graph Building Process

Despite of technology advances in natural language processing, including LLM reasoning, constructing high-quality KGs remains a challenging task. State of the art NLP pipelines often involve costly manual curation, ontology design and standardization combined with rule-based extraction methods. All these systems struggle with scalability issues and with the technical intricacies of operating complex data repositories. While semi-structured data produced by NERL tools can provide an entity inventory, LLM-enabled pipelines can further link contextual mentions to canonical entities. Still, inferring relations across diverse mentions remains a key challenge, especially in historical corpora with alias variation, multi-lingual content and specialized vocabularies.

Fig. 1 presents the proposed workflow for building a knowledge graph from historical documents with three stages of data processing steps.

The Document Pre-processing stage, prepares the required input for the LLM reasoning. The list of most relevant entities (i.e. *Entity List Extraction*) are extracted from the original text using the NERL tool developed in previous work. This ensures that the knowledge construction workflow is guided by a controlled vocabulary, allowing the human experts to validate the correctness of entity discovery in early processing steps with limited efforts. The second step in the process prepares the text from LLM reasoning. Due to the limitations imposed by LLM engines, the original text document is split in text chunks of 5.000 chars, using a sliding window and 50% of text overlapping between the chunks in order to ensure a continuous context in the following processing steps.

The Entity List provides categories and candidate canonical forms (i.e. preferred and alternative labels), while the Historical Text supplies narrative context from which relations can be inferred. This combination reflects a typical digital humanities scenario, where structured metadata and narrative sources must be brought together into a coherent representation. By including the references to the

entity references in original text and the links to controlled vocabularies (i.e. Wikidata/DbPedia), human experts are provided with the required means to validate the entity identification based on historical text and context. For example, the experiment used for validating the proposed approach is based on the *Dumitru Nistor's War Diary*, presenting author's experiences while serving in the Austrian marine during the first World War, describing his journey from Europe to Africa and Asia, being finally imprisoned in a POW camp in Japan.

LLMs are first employed in the data processing steps belonging to the *Knowledge Graph Construction* stage. They are used to identify all mentions of individual named entities into the original text and to infer the relationships between them. Differently from the NERL tools, which are using limited context from the original text, LLMs are able to identify textual mentions, even in the case when entities are referenced by pronouns (e.g. *I, he, me, my*) and not by their labels (e.g. *Dumitru Nicolau Nistor, Dumitru Nistor, Dumitru*). This enables the identification of much more actions and relationships between entities while analysing natural language resources.

Entity Normalization & Type Refinement has the goal to align the entities discovered by LLMs with the ones from the pre-computed entity List. For entities already linked with open web repositories (i.e. Wikidata), they are uniquely identified and their canonical identifier (i.e. Wikidata resource URL) is used to ensure consistency across all mentions; otherwise the Reasoning LLM is engaged to infer a suitable canonical. While the experimental evaluation is based on GPT-5, the procedure is not model-specific and can be completed by any other Reasoning LLM. Generic concepts, like *battle, ship, prison, captain, etc.* are not instantiated as nodes in the graph, but remain useful as contextual anchors for relation detection. Furthermore, entities identified by NER tools with generic category (i.e. labeled as miscellaneous by Stanford NER) are further processed to refine their type. Historical events are of particular interest for contextual analysis and knowledge graph representation of document such as war diaries. Wikidata class hierarchies are used to map specific entities to the historical event type, when their names match historically salient patterns such as battles, occupations, or armistices, following rules like:

```
(war|battle|siege|uprising|revolution|occupation|campaign|front|retreat)-> historical event
```

Alias consolidation is critical in historical corpora, where individuals and organizations may be referred to by multiple names. In the *Entity Disambiguation* step, all mentions of the same entities are unified under the canonical identity. For example, the entity identified as being "the narrator" is linked to the unique entity *Dumitru Nistor I. Nicolau*, and the same process is applied to other recurring persons or organizations where context permits confident unification. This step prevents fragmentation of entities and ensures that relational evidence aggregates consistently.

While the entities represent the nodes in the graph representation, their relationships build the edges, which are identified through the *Relation extraction validation step*. Relations are inferred at the sentence level through a hybrid strategy. Rule-based triggers detect candidate relations for categories such as TRAVELED_TO, SERVED_IN, or FAMILY. The Reasoning LLM then validates the plausibility of these candidates, enforces canonical references, and extracts supporting evidence spans. Where relevant, modes of transport (train, cart, ship) are inferred from lexical cues. Each relation is retained with its evidence, ensuring consistent interpretation and traceability and facilitating their validation using a "human in the loop" approach. This solution balances deterministic pattern recognition with flexible contextual reasoning.

Graph databases offer basic tools for navigation and visualization of knowledge graphs (see Figure 2). Therefore, the *Graph Visualization* stage prepares the results of data processing steps for importing and storage in a graph database, such as Neo4j. While the data import scripts are tool specific, the text based representation of extracted knowledge through csv files, enable their use with any computer systems with minimal efforts. Graph nodes receive dynamic labels during the import based on the entity type, while edges are annotated with type, optional attributes (e.g., mode of travel), and associated evidence. Alias consolidation guarantees that all mentions resolve to canonical identities, eliminating redundancies. By embedding evidence at the edge level, each relational claim can be traced back to the precise sentence in the historical document, ensuring transparency and enabling expert review.

4. Experimental Evaluation

4.1. Experimental Setup

The experimental evaluation is based on the (*Dumitru Nistor's War Diary*) by processing the complete entity&text corpus, including the NERL-derived *Entity List* and the full *Historical Text*. GPT-5 *Thinking* is triggered following the pipeline presented in Fig 1 to generate nodes, typed relationships, and evidence-bearing exports. The results are imported into Neo4j 2025 database. As the large number of the nodes in the graph is overwhelming, Cypher queries are employed to select sub-graphs and create meaningful graphical visualizations for human users. As an example, the most relevant entities identified in the description of the diary³ are selected using the query indicated in the Listing 1. The query may select nodes by exact string matching, alias expansion or regular expressions (i.e. regex) to retrieve all relationships among the matched set. Their interactive graphical representation is explained in subsection 4.3.

Listing 1: Validation query over selected entities

```
WITH [  
'Dumitru Nistor', 'Dumitru Nistor I. Nicolau',  
'Franz Joseph I', 'Nasud', 'Nasaud',  
'Vienna', 'Asia', 'China',  
'Japanese archipelago', 'Japan',  
'Himeji', 'Aonogahara', 'Kobe',  
'Bistria', 'Port Said', 'Pula',  
'Austro-Hungarian Navy', 'K.u.K Kriegsmarine',  
'Transylvanian militia', 'KuK Kriegsmarine',  
'SMS Kaiserin Elisabeth', 'Battle of Kiautschou'  
] AS names  
// ... (normal/regex terms, alias expansion)  
RETURN p;
```

4.2. Results

The initial processing of the complete dataset results in **3,304 entities** and **2,220 relationships**. As we aim at creating a meaningful semantic representation for historical events mentioned in the documents, the further processing performs the entity disambiguation and filtering, and builds the knowledge graph using only items linked with semantic web repositories (i.e. Wikidata, DBpedia). This will provide human users with additional insight, facilitating manual curation of entity relationships by matching them against the evidences available in linked data repositories.

Meaningful representations are generated by taking into account the document's context (e.g. descriptive metadata) selecting a set of relevant entities, as indicated in previous subsection. The resulting knowledge graphs, before and after manual curation of entity relationships, is illustrated in Fig 2. This subgraph consists of **40 nodes**, including 1 Historical Event, 19 Locations, 6 Organizations, and 14 Persons.

Table 1

Node counts after entity disambiguation and linking

Label	Count
Person	14
Location	19
Organization	6
Alias	1
Total	40

Table 2

Relationship counts after manual validation

Type	Count
TRAVELED_TO	29
TRAVELED_WITH	7
SERVED_IN	15
IS_IN	8
Other	1
Total	60

³<https://europeana.transcribathon.eu/documents/story/?story=106191>

Figure 2: Left: pruned subgraph obtained after alias consolidation and error corrections. Right: full KG visualization prior to pruning. The legend indicates node categories.

4.3. Human Oversight and Error Analysis

A total of **66 relationships** were included in the selected sub-graph for which the manual validation was performed, resulting in the identification of **6 incorrect edges**. 4 of them included false `SERVED_IN` statements for Dumitru Nistor and 2 false `IS_IN` statements for location nodes, indicating an error rate of **~9%**. This confirms the pipeline being largely reliable, but still requiring lightweight curator oversight for constructing valid knowledge graphs.

5. Conclusions and Future Research

The case study presented in this paper demonstrates the feasibility of employing reasoning LLMs to process historical documents for extracting named and building a knowledge graph representation ready to be stored in graph databases. The experimental evaluation used *GPT-5 Thinking* as reasoning model to analyze a representative war diary, which describes multiple historical events based on the authors authentic experiences during the WWI. By exploiting contextual narrative information attached to the original document and contextual information on entities linked in semantic web, human users are empowered to create meaningful visualizations and to validate the automatically constructed knowledge graph.

Early results are promising, yet the workflow continues to require a lightweight human review, particularly for edge cases and ambiguous mentions. As new reasoning models were released in the past months (e.g. Gemini 3) and other are expected to be released soon, the main focus of future work will lay on performing a comparative evaluation of different models to improve the quality of entity relationships.

At the same time, several limitations must be acknowledged. The evaluation was performed on a single, yet complex document and may not generalize to other domains or documents written in different languages, using narrative styles, or containing few references to well known named entities. Although alias consolidation and relation extraction proved generally effective, they remain sensitive to contextual ambiguities and figurative language, as reflected in the small proportion of misclassified relations that required manual correction. Moreover, the workflow relies on relatively clean input data. The performance of the proposed approach, when using noisy OCR or handwritten text recognition outputs, which are common in digital humanities repositories, was not yet investigated. Finally, the

evaluation was primarily quantitative, focusing on the identification of graph node and edges, and the meanings for graph visualization and validation. It was not benchmarking results against a ground truth, nor assessing its correctness from the perspective of domain experts.

These limitations point to several directions for further research. First, the pipeline should be scaled to larger and more diverse datasets, including multilingual corpora, to test robustness across cultural and linguistic boundaries. Second, systematic user evaluations with domain experts (e.g. historians, archivists, and digital humanists) could help to assess the trustworthiness, interpretation, and practical utility of the constructed data structure, and to build a feedback loop for enhancing the prompting design and validation support (e.g. evidence presentation, cross validation with semantic web or similar documents). Third, a comparative benchmarking and a qualitative evaluation when using alternative LLMs for knowledge graph construction frameworks would provide more insight into the capabilities and the limitations of currently available reasoning models. Finally, hybrid strategies that integrate reasoning LLMs with domain specific ontologies and formal rules may increase both reliability and explainability of the approach.

In summary, this first exploration demonstrates the potential of reasoning-LLMs for knowledge graph construction, while also highlighting: (1) the need for more comprehensive evaluation with involvement of domain experts, and (2) the need for methodological refinements to fully understand the capabilities and limitations of reasoning LLMs when used in real-world applications.

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A. Prompt Used for Knowledge Graph Extraction

The following prompt was provided to the reasoning LLM (*GPT-5 Thinking*) to guide entity alignment, alias consolidation, and relation extraction:

```
Objective
From a diary text and an entities CSV, build a Neo4j-2025-importable KG with precise relations,
promote likely events, consolidate aliases such as narrator to “**Dumitru Nistor I. Nicolau**”,
produce archive of downloadable CSVs, and return import+query instructions centered on the Narrator
.

Rules
- No clarifying questions; proceed best-effort. Perform all work now.
- Save outputs to `mnt/data/` and return links as `[file](sandbox:/mnt/data/file)`.
- Add `evidence` per relationship.

Inputs
1) Text 2) Entity CSV

Nodes
Create `nodes_specific.csv`: `name,label,`. Promote `miscvent` if name matches
`/war|battle|siege|uprising|revolution|occupation|campaign|front|retreat|armistice/i`.
Please make sure all nodes are categorised by their entity_type and not just standard entity.
Exclude overly generic entities, use them solely for relationship identification.

Relationships
Sentence-split text. Detect entities by case-insensitive `labelcanonical` (if present, else use
inference)`.
Create typed edges with `evidence` and optional `mode` (`train;cart;ship`).
- **TRAVELED_TO** (→PersonLocation) if sentence has travel verbs:
  `travel(ed|ling)|went|go|journey(ed|ing)|depart(ed|ing)|arriv(ed|ing)|left|set off|came|moved|
  sailed|rode|board(ed|ing)|cross(ed|ing)|reached`.
- `mode` keywords: train=`train|railway|railroad|carriage|wagon-lit`;
  cart=`cart|carriage|wagon|horse cart|ox cart`;
  ship=`ship|boat|vessel|steamer|steamship|barge|ferry|sail|embark`.
- **TRAVELED_WITH** (→PersonPerson) if `with|together with|along with|accompanied by`.
- **SERVED_IN** (→PersonOrganization) if `served|enlisted|mobiliz(ed)|drafted|conscripted|stationed
|posted|regiment|battalion|company|navy|army|fleet`.
- **PART_OF** (→PersonEvent) if sentence contains event keywords (see promotion) and an `event`
entity is present.
- **IS_IN** (→LocationLocation) if sentence has `in|inside|within|near|at|around|on|by` and 2
locations.
- **FRIENDS_WITH** (→PersonPerson) only if `friend(s)|comrade(s)|buddy|pal|mate`.
- **Family (directional)** only with strong evidence:
  `FATHER_OF|MOTHER_OF|BROTHER_OF|SISTER_OF|HUSBAND_OF|WIFE_OF|SON_OF|DAUGHTER_OF`
(+ detected specifics like `GRANDMOTHER_OF`).
Write `relationships_specific.csv` with columns: `start,end,type,mode,evidence`.
Use own inference, disregard deities or gods.

Alias Consolidation
Unify aliases by canonical or inference. Example: **Dumitru Nistor I. Nicolau**.
Build alias list matching `/narrator|Dumitru Nistor|Dumitru \(|Nicolau/i`;
Make sure Gods are not included.
Similar for all persons that can be certainly identified.
Save:
```

- `aliases.csv` with `alias,canonical` (canonical fixed).

Narrator Exports

Also output:

- `traveled_to.csv` (`person,location,mode,evidence`)
- `traveled_with.csv` (`person,other_person,evidence`)
- `travel_by_mode.csv` (`person,mode,location,evidence`)
- `events.csv` (`person,event,evidence`)
- `served_in.csv` (`person,organization,evidence`)
- `family.csv` (`person,counterpart,relation,direction,evidence`)
- `locations.csv` (`location`)

Offer Import Instructions for Neo4j 2025

Deliverables

Return zip file containing:

`nodes_specific.csv`, `relationships_specific.csv`, `aliases.csv`, `consolidate_narrator.cypher`,
`traveled_to.csv`, `traveled_with.csv`, `travel_by_mode.csv`,
`events.csv`, `served_in.csv`, `family.csv`, `locations.csv`.

These files MUST all be filled and contain information based on the input files supplied.

Make sure no exported files have characters that can produce errors.

Inference based on text file context + selected entities.